

Undernutrition in Children of Resource-poor Settings: Predictors, Treatment and Prevention

Ndohtabi Jerry Eyong¹, Mary Bi Suh Atanga¹, Lifoter Kenneth Navti²

¹Faculty of Health Sciences, The University of Bamenda, Cameroon

²Faculty of Science, The University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Corresponding author: Ndohtabi Jerry Eyong, The University of Bamenda, email: eyongjerry@gmail.com

Abstract

Undernutrition is a condition in which food and nutrient intakes are not adequate to meet physiological needs and maintain good health. Undernutrition remains a major public health problem, especially in children. An estimated 149 million children are stunted, 45 million are wasted and 45% of deaths in children under 5 are linked to undernutrition. The developmental, economic, social, and medical consequences of undernutrition are serious and lasting, for individuals and their families, communities, and countries, especially in resource-poor settings.

The objective of this review was to describe the predictors and to outline the best treatment and prevention strategies to combat undernutrition in children of resource-poor settings.

There is evidence of an association between birth weight, birth order, breastfeeding status, frequent illness, immunization, family size, family income, household food expenditure, sanitation, education level of parents, maternal decision-making, and undernutrition.

Treatment options include therapeutic foods and the use of antibiotics depending on the underlying cause and severity of the undernutrition. Prevention strategies must never exclude cash transfers and nutrition education.

This review has demonstrated that in resource-poor settings, access to nutritious food to combat undernutrition can be improved through interventions like cash transfers, food assistance, improved agricultural techniques, and educational programs to improve the knowledge, attitude, and practice of carers on undernutrition.

Keywords: Undernutrition, children, predictors, treatment, prevention, resource-poor settings

Introduction

Undernutrition refers to stunting, wasting, underweight and micronutrient deficiency which remains a global public health challenge, especially in children from resource-poor settings (WHO 2005). The prevalence of undernourishment climbed from 8.4% in 2019 to 9.9% in 2020 (FAO 2022). Around 45% of deaths among children under 5 years of age are linked to undernutrition. These mostly occur in low- and middle-income countries (Müller and Krawinkel 2015). In 2020, 149 million and 45 million children under 5 were stunted and wasted respectively at the global level. Also, 17 percent of preschool children are underweight and 33 percent suffer from iodine deficiency (Dukhi 2020).

Nutritional insults such as low birth weight, underweight, and stunting during critical periods of fetal and young child development produce lifelong developmental, economic, social, and medical consequences (Victoria, et al. 2008). Another serious and problematic outcome of undernutrition in resource-poor settings is the impact of early undernutrition on metabolic programming or fetal Origin of Adult Disease (FOAD). Metabolic programming is the phenomenon whereby the unborn fetus adapts to a nutrition-deficient environment because of the mother's undernourishment (Barker and David 2008). This may become problematic when the child grows up in a food-abundant or obesogenic environment as this mismatch can lead to obesity and non-communicable diseases, which already account for most of the mortality in resource-poor settings (Obiageli 2015).

In the short-term, maternal and child undernutrition are estimated to be associated with between a half and a third of global child deaths (Ezatti, et al. 2004). The contribution of undernutrition to child mortality varies by disease, being highest for diarrheal diseases (73%), and close to half for pneumonia, measles, and severe neonatal infections (Black, et al. 2008).

In 2015, the United Nations adopted a set of 17 SDGs as a universal call to action to ensure by 2030, a world free from all forms of malnutrition. Efforts to meet this target have resulted in a global decline in the burden of malnutrition but undernutrition is still on the rise. Overcoming undernutrition in resource-poor settings needs an understanding of risk factors and a scale-up of treatment and prevention strategies that have worked in similar settings (Krawinkel 2012). This write-up is thus relevant in that it describes predictors of undernutrition and the best treatment and prevention strategies in resource-poor settings.

The objectives of this review were: to describe the predictors, outline the best treatment options and prevention strategies for undernutrition in children of resource-poor settings.

I. Predictors of undernutrition among children of resource-poor settings

Undernutrition has been associated with predictors at the individual, household, and community levels. **Table 1** below provides a list of major risk factors and a description of their association with undernutrition in children of resource-poor settings.

Table 1. Description of predictors of undernutrition in resource-poor settings

Predictor	Description
Age of the child	Undernutrition is common between the ages of 6 – 24 months because, by 6 months, breast milk alone cannot cover a baby's nutrient needs, especially iron. Complementary foods started late or unsuitable for young infants may not cover the increased nutrient needs if they are not 'nutrient dense', too watery, or fed infrequently leading to undernutrition (Burgess and Louis 2008). Childhood infections at this age last longer and are more frequent and serious (WHO 2005). Children undernourished at this age are at high risk of permanently stunted growth and development (Burgess and Louis 2008).
Higher birth order	Higher birth orders (from the third, fourth, and fifth) are more likely to be stunted than lower birth orders (first and second). A parent's feelings towards a later born might hurt the child's health when these feelings contribute to conscious or unconscious neglect of the index child, resulting in inadequate nutrition, lack of parental bonding, and inattention to healthcare needs (Rahman, et al. 2015).
Low birth weight	The risk of being stunted, wasted and underweight is higher in children with low birth weight (LBW) than in those with normal birth weight due to growth failure (Peter and Morton 2019). Children with low birth weight have increased vulnerability to infections such as diarrheal and lower respiratory infections and increased risk of complications including jaundice, anemia, fatigue, and loss of appetite (Rahman, et al. 2015). This leads to poor physical growth and development.

Breastfeeding status	Breastfeeding has an impact on infectious and noninfectious disease prevention. Non-breast-fed infants, infants whose breastfeeding is not initiated within an hour after birth, and infants who are not exclusively breastfed are at greater risk of diarrheal and other infectious diseases that either affect their appetite, micronutrient absorption or increase energy needs that puts them at greater risk of undernutrition (Chisti, et al. 2011).
Frequent illness	Many illnesses can directly affect appetite, calorie absorption, or both. Loss of appetite may prevent children from eating enough food. Other illnesses also increase calorie needs. This great increase in nutrients might not be compensated by adequate intake during illness, increasing the risk of undernutrition (John 2022).
Incomplete immunization	Basic health services such as vaccination have been shown to have a protective effect against undernutrition because they prevent morbidity. (Prendergast 2015).
Family income and household food expenditure	Households with low incomes usually spend most of their total household income on food. In these cases, even the lowest out-of-pocket healthcare service can severely diminish the remaining income to be used for food supply, further perpetuating the issue of food insecurity. These low-income families cannot afford nutritious food due to unemployment, low wages, or lack of education which are associated with inadequate diet and diseases that lead to undernutrition (Siddiqui, et al. 2020).
Family size	As the family size increases, the amount of time, energy, and money spent on each available child reduces which affects the adequacy of their dietary intake. This hinders their social and physical development. Children from small families have lower risk of undernutrition than those from medium or large families and those from medium families are at lower risk of undernutrition than those from large families (Abera, et al. 2019).
Religion of household	The religious affiliation of a child's family provides information on the likely dietary restrictions encountered by a child in his or her early growing years, on the child's exposure to fasting in utero during the Muslim holy month of

	Ramadan, and the possible differences between religions in women’s autonomy and control over household resources (Brainerd and Nidhiya 2015).
Education level of parents	Parents with low education or no education are usually less exposed to information on how to prepare food with sufficient nutrients and the introduction of complementary food after 6 months may also be delayed. A previous study revealed that higher education levels lead to a higher socioeconomic status which acts as a preventive factor for undernutrition (Khattak, et al. 2017).
Unimproved sanitation	Poor water, sanitation, and hygiene increase the risk of infections, and infections influence growth. Inadequate handwashing in children increases risks of soil-transmitted helminths, diarrhea, and pneumonia which all influence growth rates in different dimensions (Dearden, et al. 2017).
Maternal decision-making power	Women's participation in decision-making influences the feeding practices of their children, which is a key determinant for undernutrition. Women's participation in healthcare decision-making is a proxy measure for a household’s overall access to healthcare which is protective against stunting prevalence. Decision-making regarding visits to her family and relatives demonstrates her mobility autonomy, which allows for greater independence and may promote access to broader resources for her children (McKenna, et al. 2019).

II. Best treatment options for undernutrition

Treatment for undernutrition depends on the underlying cause and how undernourished the child is. Antibiotics and therapeutic foods have been demonstrated to have the best treatment outcomes in resource-poor settings.

❖ Therapeutic foods

Therapeutic food is a type of nutrient-dense food used to treat acute undernutrition in children. They are lipid-based pastes, energy-dense, resist bacterial contamination, and need no cooking.

Received: 22 Feb. 2023

Revised: 3 March 2023

Final Accepted for publication: 15 March 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

They usually contain added minerals and vitamins and are an excellent source of protein and energy (Lancet 2007). Some of these therapeutic foods include ready-to-use therapeutic food (RUTF), liquid oral nutritional supplement (ONS), lipid-based nutrient supplement (LNS), large quantity lipid-based nutrient supplement (LNS-LQ), and micronutrient powder (MNP).

Therapeutic foods have been used to treat millions of children threatened by severe wasting, one of the most dangerous forms of undernutrition (Ellen and Manary 2014). Recovery rates have ranged from 80% (Lancet 2007) to 93.7% with an increase in weight, height, and MUAC (Rachel, Stephanie and Mark 2009). One of the most effective components of local therapeutic food is soybean. It is high in fiber and protein, low in saturated fat, cholesterol free, lactose-free, a good source of omega-3 fatty acids, a source of antioxidants, and high in phytoestrogens (Niyibituronsa, et al. 2014).

❖ Antibiotics

Diseases have been identified as one of the underlying causes of undernutrition. Epidemiological studies have generated evidence of a high prevalence of pneumonia, bacteremia, and urinary tract infections in children with undernutrition (Burgess and Louis 2008). This supports WHO's recommendations of broad-spectrum antibiotics for these children (WHO 2005). Recommended antibiotics include but are not limited to cotrimoxazole, ampicillin, oral amoxicillin, gentamycin, and chloramphenicol depending on the level of complication of the undernutrition, availability of the antibiotics in the setting, the response of the child to the treatment and local resistance patterns. The provision of antibiotics to severely undernourished children has been an effective strategy in resource-poor settings (Kumar, et al. 2022). The introduction of standardized regimens has significantly reduced mortality in hospitalized children (Trehan, et al. 2016).

III. Preventive strategies for undernutrition

Preventive strategies target the risk factors. Strategies such as vitamin, mineral, and micronutrient supplementation, delayed cord clamping after birth, kangaroo mother care, early initiation of breastfeeding, promotion of dietary diversity, fortifying staple foods, cash transfer programs, community-based nutrition education, and school feeding programs have shown to be effective in several settings (Burgess and Louis 2008). Preventive strategies against the risk factors are outlined in **Table 2** below.

Table 2. Preventive strategies

Predictor	Prevention	Necessary actions
-----------	------------	-------------------

Age of the child	Nutrition education	Smooth texture semi-liquids complementary foods should be introduced at approximately 6 months of age (Burgess and Louis 2008).
Higher birth order	Nutrition education on parents (Rahman, et al. 2016).	Family planning
Low birth weight	Kangaroo mother care for 1-3hours repeated at least three times a day (Evereklian and Bobbie 2017).	Adequate support for pregnant women to reduce incidence of low birth weight.
Breastfeeding status	Early initiation of breastfeeding, Nutrition education and promotion of dietary diversity (Syeda and Kingsley 2020).	Breastfeeding should be initiated within an hour after birth and continued exclusively until 6 months. Supplementary food should be introduced at 6 months and weaning done before 18 months
Frequent illness	Vitamin, mineral and micronutrient supplementation, Cash transfer programs and nutrition education (John 2022).	Prompt treatment of illnesses by addressing barriers that hinder access to care and adequate nutrient intake during illness
Incomplete immunization	Health promotion (Prendergast 2015).	Vaccination is crucial for healthy growth
Family income and household food expenditure	Cash transfer programs	Improve access to food
Family size (Number of	Cash transfer to large families (Abera, et al. 2019).	Reduce birth rates

Received: 22 Feb. 2023

Revised: 3 March 2023

Final Accepted for publication: 15 March 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

children in the household)		
Religion of household	Nutrition education (Beruk , et al. 2019).	Sensitizations to end dietary restrictions
Education level of parents	Nutrition education and school feeding programs (Khattak, et al. 2017).	The education of parents especially females be given due importance and promoted in rural and semi-urban settings
Unimproved sanitation	Education on infant and young child feeding (Dearden, et al. 2017).	Improve sanitation
Maternal decision-making power	Cash transfer to women (McKenna, et al. 2019).	Gender equality and women empowerment

From **Table 2** above, cash transfers and nutrition education can prevent many of the risk factors. The potential of cash transfer programs to improve child nutrition is because of their positive role in increasing resources for food, health, and care.

Nutritional education is any set of learning experiences designed to facilitate the voluntary adoption of eating and other nutrition-related behaviors conducive to health and well-being (Eric, et al. 2021). It provides people with correct information on the nutritional value of foods, food quality and safety, methods of preservation, processing, and handling, food preparation, and eating to help them make the best choice of foods for an adequate diet (Ayesha, et al. 2013). Nutrition education interventions with a multi-component approach that are age appropriate and of a good duration (6 months) are more likely to succeed (Murimi, et al. 2018).

Conclusion

Undernutrition remains a major public health problem in children of resource-poor settings and children unfortunately are the most at-risk group. Main predictors have been demonstrated to be age of the child, higher birth order, low birth weight, breastfeeding status, frequent illness, incomplete immunization, family income and household food expenditure, family size, religion of household, education level of parents, unimproved sanitation and maternal decision making power. Treatment options include therapeutic foods and use of antibiotics. Preventive strategies must never exclude cash transfers and nutrition education.

Recommendations

In resource-poor settings, access to nutritious food to combat undernutrition can be improved through interventions like cash transfers, food assistance, improved agricultural techniques, and educational programs to improve the knowledge, attitude, and practice of carers on undernutrition.

Competing Interest

There are no conflicts of interest in this review

References

- [1] Abera, Semaw Ferede, Johanna Kantelhardt Eva, Mulugeta Bezabihc Afewrok, Aregay Gebruc Alemseged, Ejeta Gebisa, Lauvaia Judith, Wienke Andreas, and Scherbauma Veronika. 2019. "Nutrition-specific and sensitive drivers of poor." *Global health Action* 12(1):1556572.
- [2] Alderman, Harold, Hoogeveen Hans, and Rossi Mariacristina . 2006. "Reducing Child Malnutrition in Tanzania - Combined Effects of Income Growth and Program Interventions." *Economics and Human Biology* 4(1):1-23.
- [3] Ayesha, Zahid Khan, G Rafique, H Qureshi, and Halai Badruddin Salma. 2013. "A Nutrition Education Intervention to Combat Undernutrition: Experience from a Developing Country." *ISRN Nutrition* 210287.
- [4] Barker , D JP, and J P David . 2008. "Mothers, babies and health in later life." *Edinburg* 217.
- [5] Beruk , Berhanu Desalegn, Lambert Christine, Riedel Simon, and Konrad Biesalski Hans. 2019. "Feeding Practices and Undernutrition in 6–23-Month-Old Children of Orthodox Christian Mothers in Rural Tigray, Ethiopia: Longitudinal Study." 11(1):138.
- [6] Black , R E, L H Allen , Z A Bhutta, and L E Caulfield . 2008. "Maternal and child undernutrition: global and regional exposures and health consequences." *Lancet* 243-260.
- [7] Brainerd, Elizabeth, and Menon Nidhiya . 2015. *Religion and Health in Early Childhood: Evidence from South Asia*. Population Council.
- [8] Burgess, Ann, and Danga Dr Louis. 2008. "Undernutrition in Adults and Children: causes, consequences and what we can do." *South Sudan Medical journal*.
- [9] Chisti, Mohammad J., A Salam Mohammed, Harvey Smith Jonathan, Ahmed Tahmeed, Ashraf Hasan, K Bardhan Pradip, and A.C Pietroni Mark. 2011. "Impact of Lack of Breast Feeding during Neonatal Age on the Development of Clinical Signs of Pneumonia and Hypoxemia in Young Infants with Diarrhea." *PLoS One* 6(10):e25817.
- [10] Dearden, Kirk A., Schott Whitney, T Crookston Benjamin , L Humphries Debbie , E Penny Mary, and R Behrman Jere . 2017. "Children with access to improved sanitation but not improved water are at lower risk of stunting compared to children without access: a cohort study in Ethiopia, India, Peru, and Vietnam." *BMC Public Health* 110 (2017): 7496.
- [11] Dukhi, Natisha. 2020. "Global Prevalence of Malnutrition: Evidence from Literature." *Malnutrition*.
- [12] Eric, Chee Tan, M Maluda, M Y Ibrahim, Joo Lim Kai, and Sherin Mohd Aza. 2021. "Intervention to Address Childhood Undernutrition: A Systematic Review." *Borneo Epidemiology Journal* 2(1): 3235.
- [13] Evereklian, Melvina, and Posmontier Bobbie . 2017. "The Impact of Kangaroo Care on Premature Infant Weight Gain." *Journal of pediatric nursing* 34:e10-e16.

- [14] Ezatti, Majid, D Lopez Alan, Rogers Anthony , and JL Murray Christopher. 2004. "Comparative quantification of health risks. Global and regional burden of disease attributable to selected major risk factors." *Corpus* Volume 1.
- [15] FAO. 2022. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022*. Accessed January 28, 2023. <https://www.fao.org/publications/sofi/2021/en/>.
- [16] John, E Morley. 2022. "Undernutrition." In *Disorders of nutrition*, by MSD Manual. MSD Manual.
- [17] Khattak, Umme K, P Iqbal Saima, and Ghazanfar Haider . 2017. "The Role of Parents' Literacy in Malnutrition of Children Under the Age of Five Years in a Semi-Urban Community of Pakistan: A Case-Control Study." *Cureus* 9(6): e1316.
- [18] Krawinkel, Michael. 2012. "Overcoming undernutrition with local resources in Africa, Asia and Latin America." *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 2757-2759.
- [19] Kumar, Praveen, K Chatterjee, Daniel Abner , Kumar Sinha Rajesh , and Arora Purnima . 2022. "A narrative review of efficacy of antibiotics in treatment of children with severe acute malnutrition in community based out-patient treatment." *Tropical Doctor* 52(4):489-494.
- [20] Lancet, The. 2007. "Ready-to-use therapeutic foods for malnutrition." *The Lancet* 369(9557):164.
- [21] McKenna, Caroline G., A Bartels Susan , A Pablo Lesley, and Walker Melanie. 2019. "Women's decision-making power and undernutrition in their children under age five in the Democratic Republic of the Congo: A cross-sectional study." *PLoS One* 14(12):e0226041.
- [22] Müller, O, and M C Krawinkel . 2015. "Malnutrition and health in developing countries." *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 279.
- [23] Murimi, M, F Moyeda-Carabaza Ana, Nguyen Bong, S Saha, Amin Ruhul, and V Njike. 2018. "Factors that contribute to effective nutrition education interventions in children: a systematic review." *Nutrition Reviews* 76(8):553-580.
- [24] Niyibituronsa, Marguerite, M Kyallo Florence , W Mugo Caroline, and V Gaidashova Svetlana . 2014. "Improving the nutritional status of malnourished children using soybean products in Rwanda." *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development* 14(64):13435.
- [25] Obiageli, Ezeofor Ifeyinwa. 2015. "Diagnosis of undernutrition in the first 6 months of life in Enugu city, southeast Nigeria. ." <https://theses.gla.ac.uk/7061/1/2015EzeoforPhD.pdf>.
- [26] Peter, Austin, and Ntenda Morton . 2019. "Association of low birth weight with undernutrition in preschool-aged children in Malawi." *Nutrition Journal* 18(51): 7968.
- [27] Prendergast, Andrew J. 2015. "Malnutrition and vaccination in developing countries." *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* 370(1671): 20140141.
- [28] Rachel, E Amthor, M Cole Stephanie, and J Manary Mark. 2009. "The use of home-based therapy with ready-to-use therapeutic food to treat malnutrition in a rural area during a food crisis." *Journal of the American Dietetic Association* 109(3):464-7.

- [29] Rahman, Mosfequr. 2016. "Association between order of birth and chronic malnutrition of children." *Cadernos de Saúde Pública* 32(2): 11215.
- [30] Rahman, Shafiqur, Howlader Tamanna , Shahed Masud Mohammad, and Lutfur Rahman Mohammad . 2015. "Association of Low-Birth Weight with Malnutrition in Children under Five Years in Bangladesh: Do Mother's Education, Socio-Economic Status, and Birth Interval Matter?" *PLoS ONE* 11(6):e0157814.
- [31] Siddiqui, Faareha, A Salam Rehana , S Lassi Zohra , and K Das Jai. 2020. "The Intertwined Relationship Between Malnutrition and Poverty." *Frontiers in Public Health* 8: 453.
- [32] Syeda, Batool, and Agho Kingsley. 2020. "Relationship between Breastfeeding Duration and Undernutrition Conditions Among Children Aged 0-3 Years in Pakistan." *International Journal of Paediatrics and Adolescent Medicine* 8(9611): 006.
- [33] Trehan, Indi, Goldbach Hayley S , N LaGrone Lacey , J Meuli Guthrie , and J Wang Richard. 2016. "Antibiotics as part of the management of severe acute malnutrition." *Malawi Medical Journal* 28(3):123-130.
- [34] Victora , C G, L Adair , C Fall, P C Hallal , and Martorell. 2008. "Maternal and child undernutrition: consequences for adult health and human capital." *The Lancet* 340-357.
- [35] WHO. 2005. *Pocket Book of Hospital Care for Children: Guidelines for the Management of Common Illnesses with Limited Resources*. Geneva: World Health Organisation.